

SUSTAINABLE FOREST POLICY AND CARBON SEQUESTRATION IN PAKISTAN: AN INTEGRATED ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT

Pir Aizaz Ali Shah¹, Muhammad Asif Khan², Rehan Akhtar³, Hassan Akhtar⁴,
Attiq Ur Rehman⁵, Khalid Zaman^{*6}

^{1,2,3,4,5}Department of Forestry and Wildlife Management, Faculty of Physical and Applied Sciences, The University of Haripur, Haripur, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 22620, Pakistan.

^{*6}Department of Economics, The University of Haripur, Haripur Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 22620, Pakistan.

^{*6}khalid_zaman786@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15918608>

Keywords

Forest Carbon Sequestration;
Ecosystem Services Valuation;
Environmental Awareness;
Climate Change Policy;
Sustainable Forestry Economics;
Pakistan

Article History

Received: 08 April, 2025

Accepted: 25 June, 2025

Published: 14 July, 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Khalid Zaman

Abstract

This study examines the economic value of Forest Carbon Sequestration (FCS) in Pakistan, focusing on public awareness, the impact of government policy, the economic valuation of ecosystem services, and the relationship between climate change and environmental awareness. Using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to analyze survey responses from 180 forestry, environmental science, and policy experts, the study examines the mediating role of perceived project effectiveness and the moderating role of political affiliation. The findings indicate that public awareness, government policy, and the economic valuation of ecosystem services play significant roles in shaping the economic impacts of FCS initiatives. Among all variables, climate and environmental change awareness was the most significant. Additionally, perceived effectiveness has a significant moderating effect on the relationship between public awareness and the economic returns on FCS, while political affiliation does not have a significant moderating effect. These results highlight the need for increased public participation, policy integration, and institutionalization of appreciating ecosystem services to capture the economic value of FCS better. The research offers valuable insights for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers, promoting integrated, climate-resilient forestry approaches that are climate-informed, responsive to national development agendas, and aligned with international commitments on sustainable development.

INTRODUCTION

Forests play a crucial role as climate change mitigation agents globally, owing to their potential for carbon sequestration as a natural atmospheric CO₂ sink in biomass and soils (Don et al., 2023). Carbon sequestration is now considered a key method for reducing escalating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, providing some mitigation from anthropogenic emissions (Naik & Roy, 2022). As a Natural Climate

Solution (NCS), carbon sequestration in forests plays a crucial role in climate stabilization, biodiversity conservation, and enhancing ecosystem services (Moomaw et al., 2020). Pakistan's forest systems are of ecological and economic value, occupying only 5.1% of the nation's total area, yet they face a risk of deforestation, land degradation, and unsustainable resource utilization (Khan et al., 2021). These issues

result in varying levels of carbon storage in forests, particularly in regions such as Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Gilgit-Baltistan, and the northern temperate zone. Despite Pakistan's signing of the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement, there is a lack of consistent data on carbon stock and forest biomass, making it challenging to report climate targets (Ahmad et al., 2023). These dense forest stands, characterized by high crown cover and biomass-concentrated profiles, have a high carbon sequestration potential (Ali et al., 2021a). Forests also provide resilience by managing hydrology, avoiding erosion, and promoting biodiversity (Ali et al., 2021b). The burgeoning population of Pakistan and rising energy demand are putting increased pressure on forest resources, accelerating degradation, and leading to higher emissions. Forest cover has decreased to less than 4% due to deforestation, illegal forest fires, and land use conversion to agricultural practices, making Pakistan's climate vulnerable (Zhu et al., 2024).

Pakistan has intensified efforts under REDD+ and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) to mitigate emissions and increase carbon stock (Atmadja et al., 2021). The use of market-based approaches, such as carbon trading and emission trading schemes (ETS), is also on the rise worldwide as a tool for internalizing the social cost of emissions and stimulating investment in low-carbon technology (Long & Goulder, 2023). Sustainable forestry and green entrepreneurship also provide avenues for integrating economic development with ecological sustainability (Söderholm, 2020; Olha et al., 2024). Initiatives like the Billion Tree Afforestation Programme (BTAP), developed by criteria such as the Bonn Challenge, have increased forest cover in the target regions and have the potential to enhance Pakistan's ecological footprint (Kamal et al., 2019; Sawaid et al., 2023; Asif et al., 2024). Institutional failure, top-down decision-making mechanisms, and minimal stakeholder participation are hindering the effective implementation of climate policy (Masud & Khan, 2024). The inclusion of policy, integrated planning, and strengthened governance must be instrumental in making sure that mitigation actions translate into measurable effects. Ecosystem services and forest carbon credits possess unexploited economic diversification opportunities. The absence of regional empirical analysis, however, halts the

development of evaluating the policy implications and economic viability of sequestration (Pragati & Ghosh, 2022). Carbon market readiness needs to be improved, and institutional capacity needs to be enhanced if Pakistan is to tap international finance, support sustainable land use, and fulfil its international climate commitments (Shrivastava et al., 2024; Bilal et al., 2022). Ultimately, sustainable forest management—encompassing reforestation, afforestation, and the involvement of indigenous communities—is crucial for maintaining long-term carbon stocks and preserving biodiversity (Rajasugunasekar et al., 2023; Prati & Pomero, 2022). Forest ecosystems, in this regard, are a key climate solution and an economic resource. Their potential for sequestration, as well as their economic value, must be thoroughly understood in order to incorporate forests into national policy and climate funds (Ariq et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2019).

1.1 Research Questions

The study examines the interconnections between forest carbon sequestration (FCS), its economic value, and governance and behavioural indicators in Pakistan's nascent climate policy environment. The study has the following research questions:

RQ1: To what extent do public consciousness, government national forest policies, economic valuation of ecosystem services, and environment/climate change consciousness affect the economic value of forest carbon sequestration?

The economic viability of carbon sequestration is dependent on a social, regulatory, and financial link. The development of carbon markets and offset programs is hindered by poor regulation, inadequate social awareness, and high transaction costs (Roy & Bhan, 2024; Pan et al., 2023). In Pakistan, these issues must be addressed through decentralized solutions that hybridize local traditional knowledge with current carbon offset technology in order to achieve optimal economic payback and minimize environmental impact.

RQ2: How does political affiliation mediate the relationship between public awareness and the economic impact of forest carbon sequestration?

Political alignment, therefore, plays a crucial role in making carbon markets successful due to its impact on policy adoption and public trust. Empirical evidence suggests that government support through policy incentives and subsidies can enhance carbon offsetting tools and generate higher revenues in carbon credits (Issa, 2023; Ma et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2023). Effective moderation through government commitment would make carbon finance an effective economic tool.

RQ3: How does the socially perceived efficiency of forest carbon sequestration interventions function as a mediator between forest policy and economic impacts within the context of economic valuation of forest ecosystem services?

Precision of estimation and openness in forest carbon projects are of paramount importance. Evidence suggests that the overestimation of avoided deforestation and forest management credits is due to inaccurate baselines and leakage, thereby undermining the legitimacy of carbon markets (Haya et al., 2023; West et al., 2023). Efficient stakeholder engagement and practical carbon accounting are crucial in enhancing the perceived legitimacy and financial value of such schemes.

1.2 Research Objectives

Based on the aforementioned questions, the study follows the following research objectives:

- I. To assess how public awareness, forest-related government policy, ecosystem service valuation, and environmental consciousness influence the economic impact of forest carbon sequestration in Pakistan.
- II. To examine whether political affiliation moderates the relationship between public awareness and the economic impact of forest carbon sequestration.
- III. To evaluate the mediating role of perceived effectiveness in the relationship between government policy and the economic impact of FCS, considering the role of ecosystem service valuation.

1.3. Significance of the Study

This study contributes to answering how collaboration between forest conservation and carbon

offset mechanisms can enhance climate resilience in Pakistan and unleash economic potential. With land use changing, cities expanding, and ecosystems deteriorating in a context that is conditioned by these processes, the research provides timely lessons on the role of FCS in supporting sustainable development. Zafar et al. (2023) note that the expansion of forest and cultivated land greatly increases carbon stock, highlighting the relevance of afforestation efforts like Pakistan's Billion Tree Tsunami Project, which increased forest cover by 56% between 2010 and 2020 (Goheer et al., 2023). However, despite such development, Waleed et al. (2024) report a 5% decline in national carbon storage due to urbanization at an accelerated pace, indicating the importance of integrated land-use policies. The study also points to the economic potential of the carbon market and forest carbon credit systems. By connecting FCS to economic incentives and sustainable forestry practices, Pakistan can attract new green investments and generate additional revenues. This aligns with climate finance objectives under the global economy and country resilience frameworks. Furthermore, policy suggestions from this study will help policymakers develop regulatory processes that foster open carbon markets and incentivize conservation.

By closing the gap between economic gains and climate action, this study establishes FCS as a foundation for low-carbon development, environmental integrity, and sustainable national development.

2. Literature Review

Forest carbon sequestration has emerged as a decisive element in climate change adaptation and quality economic growth. Current literature highlights its potential for environmental conservation as well as economic benefits through carbon credits. Zhang et al. (2023) present empirical findings from 2,735 Chinese cities and counties, which demonstrate how terrestrial vegetation carbon sequestration plays a crucial role in promoting quality economic development, particularly for countries with favourable industrial structures and effective environmental policies. The research highlights the application of carbon trading as well as afforestation in balancing development with sustainability targets. Forest carbon economic valuation is gaining

significant traction. Mei (2023) considers carbon credits to be among the most significant drivers of timberland returns, accounting for up to 21% of aggregate gains in a \$ 20-carbon world. Correspondingly, Verma et al. (2024) predict the high economic costs of deforestation in the Himalayas using hybrid modelling frameworks, highlighting the importance of sustainable forest management and carbon offset schemes. Russo et al. (2023) predict economic valuations for forest ecosystem services using carbon market prices as a measure to support integrated governance and PES in order to increase financial profitability.

Policy at the government level is essential to driving forest carbon outcomes. Meng et al. (2023) construct a Climate Change Policy Attention (CCPA) index and demonstrate that consistent, anticipatory policies play a crucial role in maintaining forest carbon pools through renewable energy and green investment. Shen et al. (2023) conducted a meta-analysis of 88 forest carbon market-based instruments (MBIs). They categorized institutional roles into buyer, seller, regulator, and facilitator types, highlighting the effectiveness of combined policy tools over single ones. Afforestation for economic and climate change mitigation purposes is also recommended in some research. For instance, Yadav and Yadav (2023) suggest afforestation on agricultural land, supported by government incentives, to enhance carbon stocks and rural incomes. Suhardono et al. (2024) estimate enormous biomass and carbon stock in special-purpose forest land, attributing a carbon credit price of \$70.12/ha. Liu et al. (2023) project future wood carbon sequestration under socioeconomic conditions and calculate that regrowth forests may contribute 5% of anthropogenic emissions. Subsidies and carbon pricing are crucial in influencing landowner behaviour. Szajko et al. (2024) and Kocaglu et al. (2024) propose that subsidies and increased carbon prices encourage afforestation, lower emissions, and enhance sequestration. Meanwhile, political identity and environmental concerns inform people's beliefs about climate policies, as stated by Wester and Macdonald (2023). Social capital and political ideology are essential for promoting public participation in carbon mitigation, as noted by Hao et al. (2023).

Ecosystem services valuation is also getting more methodologically advanced. Brander et al. (2024) aggregate 9,400 dollar estimates within the ESVD and highlight the importance of standardization and site-specific corrections. Mirici and Berberoglu (2024) employ the InVEST model and the Social Cost of Carbon (SCC) to value rural carbon, suggesting the spatial integration of land-use planning. Methodological and technological advancements are improving measurement precision. Gelaye (2024) and Li et al. (2022) propose Tier 3 methodology and model-based forest management methods, respectively, to enhance the precision of carbon stock estimation. Zijie Ji (2023) employs PCA, neural networks, and decision-making models to optimize sequestration at various levels of forest management. REDD+ and CFPs (Carbon Forestry Projects) are also researched. Andrews & Mulder (2024) demonstrate how previous REDD+ exposure influences future willingness to conserve, even in the face of project failure. In contrast, Nantongo et al. (2024) find that REDD+ enhances income and sequestration from forests. Pakina (2024) recommends afforestation as a cheaper alternative to reforestation in decarbonization programs and vows to maximize CFPs for both climate and economic benefits. Wider systemic views are presented by Enriquez-de-Salamanca (2024), who identifies ecological and social costs associated with sequestration plans, and Raihan (2023), who advocates for circular economy approaches and public-private partnerships in forest management. Setiawan et al. (2024) and Lungarska & Chakir (2024) point out that LULC (Land Use and Land Cover) processes and land adjustment are key factors to ecosystem resilience and carbon sequestration. Lastly, Block et al. (2024) identify economic incentives, social influence, and policy knowledge as the key determinants of farmers' involvement in humus-based carbon schemes.

2.1 Research Gaps and Contribution of the Study

Although recognition of forest carbon sequestration (FCS) has been growing as a two-edged sword for climate mitigation as well as country development, research gaps remain significant in terms of its economic implications, policy role, public awareness, and political processes in developing nations like Pakistan. Past studies have not yet addressed the

institutionalization of FCS in national climate policy, nor have they examined how governance regimes, market structures, or public engagement influence its feasibility and long-term sustainability. Chowdhury and Brown (2023) refer to market-based incentives for FCS, noting increases in forest stock and revenue, but also observe that smallholder participation is constrained. Their research does not go far enough in examining economic trade-offs and institution-supported, more long-term support. This research plugs these gaps by adopting an economic potential approach to FCS for small-scale forest owners with carbon market access and land-use trade-offs. Kasim and Ghassan (2023) provide informative carbon dynamics modelling in the forest but fail to incorporate economic valuation and market integration of sequestration in developing contexts. The present study aims to connect financial opportunities for landowners with forest carbon, identifying the market instruments and policy mechanisms required to monetize sequestration sustainably. Although Low et al. (2024) discuss global perceptions of carbon removal, they do not address the impact of disinformation and ignorance on FCS participation in developing nations. This research fills the gap by exploring public awareness and its impact on participation in Pakistan's FCS programs. Regmi et al. (2023) prioritize forest policy and community governance but do not consider the role of government policies in balancing sequestration with economic development at the national level. This study examines how regulatory frameworks and incentive systems can facilitate socially equitable, economically sustainable, and carbon-neutral forestry activities.

In the same vein, ChayAsdak (2023) gives a background of Indonesia's sustainable forest policies but does not examine FCS as a financial tool. The current research builds upon existing studies by examining policy design—specifically, benefit-sharing and incentives—and how it can enhance Pakistan's carbon management and facilitate market entry. Balasubramanian and Sangha (2023) appreciate forest ecosystem services in the Western Ghats but not FCS separately for economic valuation or market participation. The research provides economic valuation of forest carbon as a distinct, tradable ecosystem service, thus enhancing practice in

valuation and informing incentive-based forest conservation. Lambjad et al. (2024) examine environmental awareness but not its contribution to FCS adoption. Through their exploration of awareness as an impetus for carbon market participation, this research adds policy and learning behavioural elements. Cai et al. (2023) evaluate A&R movements in China without considering the influence of political parties. A political party is examined as a moderator with an impact on legislative and financial support towards FCS, employing a critical governance factor. West et al. (2023) criticize the technical underperformance of avoided-deforestation schemes, but they omit the role of perceived effectiveness in determining stakeholder trust. This study examines the impact of perception on participation, investment, and long-term engagement in FCS programs. Geographically, studies such as those conducted by Feitosa et al. (2023), Cherinet and Lemi (2023), and Jariyapong et al. (2023) offer economic valuations of carbon sequestration in the Amazon, Ethiopia, and Thailand. Notwithstanding this, Pakistan is significantly underrepresented empirically in FCS analysis. The gap is filled by assessing local carbon dynamics, economic potential, and policy regimes. Carbon pricing for Brazil is further explored by Assunção et al. (2023), but Pakistan's specific deforestation issues, poor policy enforcement, and market availability are not addressed. This study provides much-needed country-level analysis for integrating FCS into Pakistan's climate and economic policy agenda.

2.2. Contribution of the Study

The current study has several contributions to the literature:

Economic Valuation and Market Integration: The study assesses the economic value of FCS for Pakistani smallholder forest owners, examining how participation in the carbon market and financial tools can be strengthened to facilitate fair revenue collection.

Policy Coordination and Institutional Change: The research evaluates the role of government policies in mainstreaming FCS into Pakistan's climate agenda and economic development policy, with emphasis on

changes that will enhance policy coherence and involvement of small farmers.

- **Public Awareness and Involvement:** This examines how awareness levels, misperceptions, and information access influence FCS community involvement, informing effective communication and education approaches. Policies.

- **Political Moderation:** Political alignment is offered as a moderator that affects policy support, regulatory choice, and public acceptability—so far unexamined in FCS studies.

- **Perceived Effectiveness and Trust in Stakeholders:** This examines how the perceived effectiveness or ineffectiveness of carbon projects affects public trust, investment, and long-term engagement, thereby enhancing accountability and performance measures.

- **Regional Relevance to Pakistan:** This research bridges a regional gap by presenting a local, multi-dimensional approach that appropriates economic, policy, and social aspects of FCS to support national climate action and forest sustainability.

With an interdisciplinary strategy that incorporates economic valuation, governance analysis, behavioural research, and political considerations, this research presents a balanced methodology for understanding and facilitating forest carbon sequestration in Pakistan.

2.3 Hypotheses Development

Based on the stated literature review, the following research hypotheses have been formulated i.e.,

H1: Public awareness of forest carbon sequestration and government policies on forest management have a positive impact on the economic impact of forest carbon sequestration.

H2: Environmental and climate change awareness, as well as the economic valuation of forest ecosystem services, have a positive impact on the economic benefits of FCS.

H3: Political affiliation moderates the interaction between public awareness of FCS and government policies on forest management.

H4: FCS Project perceived effectiveness mediates economic valuation of forest ecosystem services and environmental and climate change awareness.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

The study employs two primary theoretical frameworks in analyzing the economic and environmental aspects of forest carbon sequestration (FCS), i.e., Carbon Taxation and Market-Based Environmental Regulation Theory and Natural Capital Theory.

2.4.1 Carbon Taxation and Market-Based Environmental Regulation Theory

Carbon pricing and market-based environmental regulation have become the central strategies within the international climate governance system, facilitating emissions reduction and economic stability. The empirical data of Colmer et al. (2024) confirm the success of the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), which effectively reduced CO₂ emissions by 14–16% without affecting economic production, rather than shifting emission-intensive activities, companies invested in clean technology, substantiating the hypothesis that market-based regulation is the driver of innovation without undermining economic stability.

This theoretical framework is also supported by Siddique et al. (2023), who analyzed 500 foreign companies and found that these policy actions significantly improve carbon performance, especially in highly emissions-intensive sectors. However, their implications for carbon disclosure are still constrained. Tu and Shi (2023) support this claim in the Chinese context, illustrating how carbon trading policies stimulate high-quality innovation, particularly among non-state-owned enterprises and those with lower levels of financialization. Chang et al. (2023) provide further empirical evidence based on a spatial econometric analysis of China's provinces, suggesting that environment policies driven by investment—specifically, green knowledge innovation policies—are most effective in stimulating long-term emission reductions. Likewise, Ramani et al. (2024), using a game-theoretic model, demonstrate that hybrid policies comprising carbon taxes, subsidies, and lump-sum transfers can achieve socially optimal emissions abatement while also ensuring firm profitability and social welfare.

Together, these contributions highlight the catalytic role of market-based instruments in not only reducing carbon intensity but also in promoting green firm

innovation and enhancing policy effectiveness. They provide a robust theoretical basis for assessing FCS in economic models that balance environmental conservation with market incentives—especially relevant in developing countries such as Pakistan, where forest-based mitigation opportunities are underutilized.

2.4.2 Natural Capital Theory

Natural Capital Theory views ecosystems as foundational economic assets, providing a range of physical and intangible services that enhance well-being and promote sustainable development in society. Forests, as sinks for carbon and areas of biodiversity, form the foundation of this framework. Martino et al. (2024) emphasize participatory and place-based valuation methods in the appraisal of forest ecosystems, moving away from traditional monetary valuation toward cultural and relational values that influence land-use decisions. Garcia et al. (2024) emphasize the importance of both informal and formal education in promoting sustainable natural forest capital management, highlighting its role in raising awareness about forest ecosystem services. They highlight how combining ecological and cultural values within environmental education enhances conservation behaviour and policy support. Blachly et al. (2024), in a sample of 700 watersheds across the United States, illustrate how government land management maintains synergies among natural capital stocks, such as forests, water supply, and rangelands, more intact than private ownership of land, which prioritizes trade-offs. Such evidence supports public intervention and planning based on the principles of conserving natural capital.

Kirey and Morozova (2023) identify difficulties in valuing non-market forest values—e.g., cultural heritage and scientific value—and urge more economical approaches to enhance the incorporation of such values into sustainable development strategies. In Concord, Baskent (2023) estimates and maps key ecosystem services in Turkish forests, putting their total economic value at over \$624 million. His research confirms that economic and spatial valuation techniques are essential for informing forest policy management and striking a balance between conservation and productive use.

Together, this literature affirms the role of Natural Capital Theory in assessing FCS not just as a climatic mitigation measure but as a systemically sophisticated ecosystem service of considerable economic and social value. This enables policymakers to assign value, rank, and conserve forests based on their significant contributions to national assets and environmental resilience.

3. Methodology

3.1. Study Population

The study population of the research is university lecturers, administrative officials, forest officials, and postgraduate and graduate students with theoretical or practical knowledge in environmental science, forestry, or climate change. The sample is respondent-based based on qualification, ability, and direct or indirect participation in forest management or carbon sequestration schemes. Forest officials are prime players, as they are directly involved in managing forest resources, enforcing forestry legislation, and implementing carbon sequestration activities. Their on-the-job experience offers sound insights into matters of operations and the bottom-line benefits of carbon storage in forests. Academics in universities and foresters, sustainability researchers, and environmental economists make theoretical and analytical contributions that enhance scientific and economic assessment of forest carbon sequestration. Administrative staff in environmental agencies and forestry policy units offer information on regulatory procedures and policy compliance on carbon offsetting and valuation of the environment. The inclusion of postgraduate and graduate students pursuing relevant courses such as environmental science, forestry, and economics provides a diversity of perspectives from early academic minds to field-level minds. Their problem-solving mind and conceptual mind make them more than capable of seeing FCS from a holistic point of view, along with its economic implications. Diversity among participants guarantees critical testing in which theoretical skills are integrated with practical experience.

3.2. Sample of the Study

The research utilizes purposive sampling to recruit 180 respondents with the required knowledge and

interest in FCS and economic aspects. Information-rich participants based on non-probability sampling can provide credible and context-relevant information. Data was collected from various institutions with established programs in forestry, environmental sciences, economics, and climate science. Sample research institutes and universities are:

- I. University of Peshawar
- II. Pakistan Forest Institute (PFI), Peshawar
- III. University of Haripur
- IV. Hazara University
- V. University of Agriculture Faisalabad
- VI. Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad
- VII. University of the Punjab, Lahore
- VIII. COMSATS University Islamabad, Abbottabad Campus
- IX. Karakoram International University, Gilgit
- X. Gomal University, D.I. Khan
- XI. BUIITEMS, Quetta

In such organizations, information has been gathered from field surveys and electronic media (e.g., Google Forms and institutional email networks) through professional networks like students, researchers, and scholars. Target departments are Forestry and Wildlife Management, Environmental Sciences, Economics, Geography, and Climate Change Studies. This method offers diversification in terms of academic fields and geographical sites.

3.3. Data Collection Technique

Standardized questionnaires were used as the primary tool to collect data. Questionnaires are firmly established to produce standardized, measurable, and comparable information from various groups of respondents. The questionnaire includes closed questions and Likert-scale items that identify salient themes: carbon sequestration in forests, carbon market participation, economic valuation of forest benefits, policy contexts, and stakeholder perceptions towards carbon offset schemes.

Prior to the full data collection, the study conducted a pilot study to validate clarity, content validity, and response consistency. The pilot sample participants consist of forestry experts, environmental economists, and climate change researchers. Revisions to improve question framework and context-appropriateness

guided by feedback. Data collection then proceeds through both personal visits and online surveys in order to ensure broad participation and inclusiveness.

3.4. Variables and Measurement

The economic effect of forest carbon sequestration is studied as the dependent variable, while the independent variables are:

- I. Public Awareness of Forest Carbon Sequestration
- II. Government Forest Management Policies
- III. Forest Ecosystem Services Economic Value
- IV. Environmental Awareness and Climate Change

The study further incorporates:

- I. Political Party Membership as a moderator variable, noting its effect on FCS attitude and policy support.
- II. Perceived Effectiveness of FCS Projects as an intermediary variable, as it acts with the specific function of determining trust, willingness to invest, and policy support.

All variables were based on a five-point Likert scale:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

These variables capture fundamental constructs that underpin the economic and institutional success of forest carbon sequestration projects. Public consciousness is needed to combine community participation and efficient government actions to form the foundation of regulatory backstops. Economic valuation of ecosystem services gives legitimation to conservation-driven investment, and climate consciousness promotes expanded environmental conduct. Political alignment is a mediator of stakeholder attitudes, and perceived project success mediates economic performance.

3.5. Statistical Techniques

To effectively examine interrelationships between study variables, the following statistical methods were used:

i. Frequency Distribution and ANOVA

Frequency distributions will measure the frequency of response on the Likert scale. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) will examine whether perceptions vary significantly by respondent categories (e.g., forest officers and university teachers).

ii. Factor Analysis

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was used to lower the dimension and reveal underlying latent constructs with groups of similar variables. It simplifies the dataset and enhances the interpretability of underlying patterns.

iii. Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was used to examine the direct effects of independent variables on the economic effect of FCS. Regression coefficients show the significance, size, and direction of effects, outlining policy-implementation empirical directions.

iv. Moderation Analysis

Moderation analysis examines whether political affiliation qualitatively modifies the association

between public awareness/government policy and the economic effect of FCS. Interaction terms were incorporated to detect conditional effects.

v. Mediation Analysis

Mediation analysis quantifies the extent to which the perceived success of FCS projects mediates the association between public awareness or environmental awareness and economic effect. Bootstrapping methods were utilized to confirm indirect effects and detect significant pathways.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the demographic survey of the respondents.

Table 1: Demographic Survey

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	63	63.0
	Female	37	37.0
Age	19-30 years	86	86.0
	31-40 years	07	7.0
	41-50 years	03	3.0
	More than 50 years	04	4.0
Education Level	Bachelor's Degree	52	52.0
	Master's Degree	38	38.0
	PhD or higher	10	10.0
Role/Position	University Professor	4	4.0
	Faculty Member	29	29.0
	Administrative Staff	12	12.0
	Forest Staff	32	32.0
	Local Politician	11	11.0
	Local Journalist	12	12.0
Experience	0-5 years	85	85.0
	6-10 years	5	5.0
	11-15 years	3	3.0
	16+ years	7	7.0

Table 1 show the demographic composition of respondents who participated in the research. One hundred and eighty individuals were polled. The breakdown by gender stands at 63% male respondents and 37% female respondents. The largest group of respondents (86%) falls in the age bracket 19–30, which reveals a young respondent group.

Educationally, most of them possess a bachelor's degree (52%), followed by a master's degree (38%) and a minority with PhDs or higher (10%). Respondent jobs are also varied, such as forest staff (32%), academics (29%), administrative officers (12%), local journalists (12%), local politicians (11%), and university lecturers (4%). In terms of experience, most

(85%) have 0–5 years of work experience, indicating a relatively early-stage population. Table 2 shows the item’s frequency distribution.

Table 2: Item’s Frequency Distribution

Variables	Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Dependent Variable: Economic Impact of Forest Carbon Sequestration (EIFCS)	I believe that forest carbon sequestration has significant economic benefits for Pakistan	10%	3%	9%	40%	38%
	Forest conservation and carbon sequestration could lead to new economic opportunities in sectors such as agriculture, tourism, and forestry.	13%	2%	4%	44%	37%
	Forest carbon sequestration contributes positively to reducing economic losses caused by climate change.	6%	6%	15%	46%	27%
Independent Variables 1: Public Awareness of Forest Carbon Sequestration (PAFCS)	I am aware of the concept of carbon sequestration and its role in combating climate change.	3%	3%	17%	57%	20%
	I understand the economic implications of forest carbon sequestration in Pakistan.	5%	11%	21%	41%	22%
	There is enough public information available on how forest carbon sequestration can	17%	23%	18%	26%	16%

	benefit the economy.					
Independent Variable 2: Government Policies on Forest Management (GPFM)	I believe the government is actively promoting forest carbon sequestration as a strategy for economic development.	17%	26%	25%	24%	8%
	Existing government policies support forest conservation and carbon sequestration efforts effectively.	10%	36%	24%	22%	8%
	Government policies on forest management are well-integrated with the country's climate change and economic policies.	12%	30%	14%	33%	11%
Independent Variable 3: Economic Valuation of Forest Ecosystem Services (EVFES)	Forest ecosystems provide significant economic value through services like carbon sequestration, biodiversity, and water regulation.	6%	10%	11%	53%	30%
	The economic contribution of forest ecosystems is underappreciated in Pakistan's economic policies.	3%	2%	15%	58%	22%
	Forest conservation policies should consider the full economic value of ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration.	3%	1%	13%	60%	23%
Independent Variable 4: Environmental	I believe that climate change is a major issue that	2%	0%	9%	40%	49%

and Climate Change Awareness (ECCA)	requires immediate action, including forest carbon sequestration efforts.					
	There is sufficient awareness about the relationship between deforestation, carbon emissions, and climate change in my community.	13%	19%	17%	34%	17%
	I am aware that forest carbon sequestration can play a significant role in mitigating climate change.	4%	3%	8%	44%	41%
Moderating Variable (Independent Variable 5): Political Affiliation (PA)	My political views influence my perception of forest conservation and carbon sequestration policies.	7%	21%	24%	40%	8%
	Political leaders should prioritize forest carbon sequestration as part of climate change mitigation policies.	7%	5%	9%	45%	34%
	Political factors significantly impact the implementation of carbon sequestration initiatives in my region.	7%	10%	16%	43%	24%
Mediator Variable (Independent Variable 6): Perceived Effectiveness of Forest Carbon Sequestration	I believe that forest carbon sequestration projects are effective in reducing carbon emissions and mitigating climate change.	4%	3%	14%	41%	38%

Projects (PEFCSP)	Forest carbon sequestration projects are likely to generate significant long-term economic benefits for Pakistan.	4%	5%	8%	51%	32%
	I trust that forest carbon sequestration efforts are well-managed and effectively contribute to the country's climate goals.	5%	10%	8%	44%	33%

The respondents were requested to measure their degree of agreement or otherwise with every statement on a five-point Likert scale. The pattern of responses shows that most participants were inclined towards agreement with the statements, indicating a generally positive view of forest carbon sequestration and its economic, environmental, and policy implications. Table 3 displays the overall variance explained for each component within factor analysis, using the principal component extraction method.

Table 3: Factor Analysis

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.913	32.918	32.918	6.913	32.918	32.918
2	2.191	10.432	43.350	2.191	10.432	43.350
3	1.907	9.079	52.429	1.907	9.079	52.429
4	1.303	6.207	58.636	1.303	6.207	58.636
5	1.205	5.738	64.373	1.205	5.738	64.373
6	1.129	5.377	69.750	1.129	5.377	69.750

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The first five components cover a cumulative variance of 64.373%, with the first component explaining 32.918% of the overall variance. The additional components continue to add smaller percentages to the overall variance. The empirical analysis in Table 4 highlights several statistically significant relationships that provide deeper insights into the economic impact of forest carbon sequestration (EIFCS) and its key influencing variables.

Table 4: Regression Analysis

Variables	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
Experience	.128	1.112	.049
PAFCS	.520	4.418	.000
GPFM	-.121	-1.342	.183
EVFES	.317	3.141	.002
ECCA	.004	.036	.971
PA	.170	1.709	.090

PEFCSP	-.109	-.959	.340
Statistical Tests			
R ²	.474	ANOVA F-Test	13.955
Adjusted R ²	.440	Prob. F-value	.000

4.1 Experience and Economic Impact of Forest Carbon Sequestration (EIFCS)

The variable Experience demonstrates a **positive and statistically significant association** with EIFCS ($\beta = 0.128, t = 1.112, p = 0.049$). This finding suggests that individuals with greater professional experience in forestry, environmental management, or related fields contribute more effectively to carbon sequestration initiatives. Their cumulative knowledge of forest carbon dynamics, carbon credit schemes, and sustainable management strategies enhances the economic efficacy of these projects. Experienced professionals are better equipped to navigate technical and policy-related complexities, making them crucial agents in maximizing both environmental and economic returns from sequestration efforts.

4.2 Potential for Afforestation and Forest Carbon Sequestration (PAFCS)

A particularly strong and highly significant relationship was observed between the Potential for Afforestation and Forest Carbon Sequestration and EIFCS ($\beta = 0.520, t = 4.418, p < 0.001$). This underscores the transformative role of afforestation and reforestation as long-term climate solutions with high economic yield. For example, afforestation efforts in northern China are projected to generate up to **105.38 Mt** of additional carbon sinks by 2050, equating to an economic valuation of **US\$17.68 billion** (Sun et al., 2023). Furthermore, carbon sinks in Chinese forests are expected to offset **13.2–18.2%** of national emissions between 2021 and 2060, with market mechanisms potentially increasing this by up to 5.6% (Ke et al., 2023). Regional variations also exist; for instance, afforestation in Southwest China offers a **relatively cost-efficient model** (Ge et al., 2023).

While afforestation offers high long-term environmental and financial returns, it faces **barriers in the form of upfront capital requirements, delayed payback periods, and financial risk**, especially in resource-constrained settings. Therefore, unlocking the full economic potential of afforestation depends

on well-targeted financial incentives and regionally nuanced policy interventions.

4.3 Economic Valuation of Forest Ecosystem Services (EVFES)

The study finds a **moderate but statistically significant positive relationship** between Economic Valuation of Forest Ecosystem Services and EIFCS ($\beta = 0.317, t = 3.141, p = 0.002$). This affirms that recognizing and monetizing ecosystem services—such as carbon storage, biodiversity conservation, and hydrological regulation—can substantially enhance the economic rationale for investing in forest-based climate mitigation strategies.

Quantifying these services strengthens the economic case for sustainable forest management (Başkent, 2023), enabling policymakers and conservationists to justify resource allocation and attract financial support. However, **risks of overvaluation or misvaluation** should not be overlooked, as these could lead to inflated expectations and misallocation of resources. Nonetheless, when carefully and accurately assessed, ecosystem service valuation remains a cornerstone for aligning economic and ecological priorities in forest governance (Nolander & Lundmark, 2024).

4.4 Protected Areas (PA) and EIFCS

The association between Protected Areas and EIFCS was **positive but marginally significant** at the 10% level ($\beta = 0.170, t = 1.709, p = 0.090$). The positive beta coefficient suggests that protected areas may contribute to improved economic outcomes in carbon sequestration projects. Globally, PAs hold about **26% of terrestrial woody carbon**, with an additional **9.65 Gt** of carbon attributed to their protected status (Duncanson et al., 2023). In Brazil’s Amazon, the ARPA initiative significantly reduced deforestation, leading to avoided emissions of over **104 MtCO₂** (Soares-Filho et al., 2023). The relatively modest statistical association in this study could be attributed to the **delayed economic realization** from PAs, given their conservation-focused mandate and the high

costs of establishment and maintenance. Nonetheless, the **long-term ecological integrity and carbon storage stability** provided by PAs justifies continued investment and policy support.

4.5 Literature Contextualization

These findings are consistent with emerging literature emphasizing the **triple role of forests**—as carbon sinks, economic assets, and biodiversity havens. Mei (2023) identifies multiple revenue streams for timberland investment, including forest carbon markets. Daigneault et al. (2024) demonstrate that carbon sequestration can coexist with sustained timber harvests, provided that forest management is carefully

balanced. Yin (2024) further elaborates on challenges such as carbon accounting accuracy, regional disparities, and governance gaps in achieving effective forest carbon storage globally.

Collectively, these findings support a **multi-dimensional approach** to forest carbon sequestration—one that simultaneously advances **economic development, ecological sustainability, and climate resilience**. The integration of experiential knowledge, afforestation potential, ecosystem service valuation, and protected area management offers a holistic framework for scaling up forest-based climate strategies, particularly in developing contexts. Table 5 shows the moderation-Item’s analysis.

Table 5: Moderation Item’s Analysis

Variables	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
EIFCS	////	4.321	.000
My political views influence my perception of forest conservation and carbon sequestration policies.	.100	1.053	.295
Political leaders should prioritize forest carbon sequestration as part of climate change mitigation policies.	.362	3.615	.000
Political factors significantly impact the implementation of carbon sequestration initiatives in my region.	-.028	-.283	.778
Statistical Tests			
R ²	.140	ANOVA F-Test	5.216
Adjusted R ²	.113	Prob. F-value	.002

The variable "Political leaders ought to make forest carbon sequestration a priority within climate change mitigation strategies" reveals a positive and significant association with the Economic Impact of Forest Carbon Sequestration (EIFCS). The standardized coefficient of the variable is Beta = 0.362, t-value = 3.615, and the p-value is 0.000 (Table 4.6). These findings imply that when political leaders give greater emphasis to forest carbon sequestration as part of climate change mitigation efforts, it has a positive

impact on the economic implications of carbon sequestration activities. This suggests that political endorsement and policy priority can make forest carbon sequestration more effective and economically viable.

This conclusion is supported by existing studies, with the need for political support highlighted for the realization of the maximum gains from forest carbon sequestration. Current research emphasizes the important contribution of forest carbon sequestration

to climate change mitigation and sustainable development. Li et al. (2025) reported that China's forest carbon stocks rose by 93.2% between 2000 and 2022, with a positive contribution to sustainable development goals. State-owned forest farms (SFFs) are important for forest management and carbon sequestration improvement (Gao et al., 2025). Yet the efficiency of SFF investment differs between regions and follows diminishing returns after optimal levels. The REDD+ mechanism in tropical rainforests shows that socio-economic change influences carbon

emissions mainly through changes in land use (Lu et al., 2025). Assessing the efficiency of forestry carbon sink projects, You et al. (2025) highlighted management capacity and climate factors as contributing to affecting state-owned forest farms' performance. These results highlight the need for maximizing carbon sequestration benefits through forest investment and policy optimization and for supporting climate change mitigation. Table 6 shows the Mediation-based Item's Analysis.

Table 6: Mediation-based Item's Analysis

Variables	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
EIFCS	~~~~	4.348	.000
I believe that forest carbon sequestration projects are effective in reducing carbon emissions and mitigating climate change.	.092	.790	.432
Forest carbon sequestration projects are likely to generate significant long-term economic benefits for Pakistan.	.340	2.455	.016
I trust that forest carbon sequestration efforts are well-managed and effectively contribute to the country's climate goals.	.035	.300	.764
Statistical Tests			
R ²	.180	ANOVA F-Test	7.030
Adjusted R ²	.155	Prob. F-value	.000

The variable Forest carbon sequestration projects are likely to provide considerable long-term economic returns to Pakistan reveals a positive and significant association with the Economic Impact of Forest Carbon Sequestration (EIFCS). The beta coefficient of this variable is Beta = 0.340, with a t-value = 2.455, while the p-value is 0.016 (Table 4.7). These findings indicate that those who are of the opinion that forest carbon sequestration projects have the potential to bring huge long-term economic returns to Pakistan perceive a greater economic effect of such projects.

This positive correlation between the perceived economic benefits and the economic returns of forest carbon sequestration is consistent with international observations. For example Carbon sequestration in Brazil's Amazon can create societal values of US\$21.85 million by 2050 (Feitosae et al.,2023). Voluntary carbon markets have picked up in the United States, where afforestation/reforestation projects are producing more units of offset credits than avoided conversion projects (Cho et al., 2025). Under the contemporary conditions of climate

change, within the context of market and non-market strategies, numerous instruments and solutions have been developed, targeted at adapting to such changes, reducing climate risks, and stimulating low-carbon economic growth (Morkovina et al., 2023).

5. Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

The objective of this study was to investigate the economic influence of forest carbon sequestration, with emphasis on how public awareness, government policies, forest ecosystem service valuation, and awareness of climate change affect this influence. The political affiliation as a moderator and perceived efficiency of carbon sequestration projects as a mediator were also examined to determine the causation relationships. The main goals of the study were to measure the direct effect of public awareness, government policy, economic valuation of forest ecosystem services, and environmental/climate change awareness on the economic effect of forest carbon sequestration, while also examining the mediating effect of perceived effectiveness and the moderating effect of political affiliation. This study was done in Pakistan, where forest-based carbon sequestration programs are increasingly becoming relevant in climate and economic policy debates. The research focused on a sample population of 180 respondents consisting of students, professionals, and community members involved with forestry, environmental sciences, and policy implementation. Key results indicated that public awareness, government policy, and economic valuation of ecosystem services have a significant influence on perceived and actual economic effect of forest carbon sequestration, with public awareness ($\beta = 0.315$), government policy ($\beta = 0.253$), and economic valuation ($\beta = 0.273$) all having strong positive correlations. Environmental awareness was also significantly influential, as evidenced by the highest mean score ($M = 4.1403$) among variables. Additionally, perceived effectiveness was a powerful mediating variable between the independent variables and the economic effect, while political affiliation was not a significant moderator of these relationships, indicating that the core variables' effects were similar across political perspectives. Overall, public awareness and policy structures need to be improved in order to achieve the maximum economic value of forest

carbon sequestration. This research highlights the relevance of ecosystem service valuation and environmental education as instruments of effective forest management. The results underpin the necessity for science-based and participative solutions to forest-based climate policy in Pakistan and elsewhere.

5.1. Policy Recommendations

5.1.1 Short-Term Policy Recommendations

Short term, the public should be educated and informed about forest carbon sequestration to enhance its economic effect. Non-governmental organizations and government institutions need to come together and implement focused awareness campaigns in local languages and through mediums like radio, community centers, mosques, and schools—particularly in those areas with rich forests like Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Gilgit-Baltistan, and Azad Jammu & Kashmir. At the same time, government policies regarding forest management need to be revised to incorporate near-term incentives like carbon credit pilot schemes, funding for afforestation under the Ten Billion Tree Tsunami Program, and ease of local engagement in REDD+ and other carbon financing initiatives. Institutionalization of the economic valuation of forest ecosystem services should also be done by forestry departments at the provincial level, and integrated into district development planning, so that local governments are able to identify and account for economic benefits from the forest. These measures, fueled by enhanced climate change communication and inter-agency coordination, can stimulate bottom-up support and short-term economic benefits.

5.1.2. Medium-Term Policy Recommendations

For sustained outcomes, the perception of the effectiveness of forest carbon sequestration projects has to be dealt with at program and institutional levels. The Ministry of Climate Change and provincial forest agencies should ensure transparency and credibility by means of third-party evaluations carried out at regular intervals, the utilization of satellite monitoring equipment (like Forest Resource Assessment via GIS), and availability of project results to the public. Capacity building must be provided to district officials, forest officers, and local councils for

enhancing project delivery and communication of success stories. Setting up village-level carbon committees, particularly in forest and tribal areas, will improve trust and participation. Incorporating these mechanisms into Pakistan's national climate change and forestry policies will enhance public confidence in project results and encourage increased investment by development agencies and the private sector in carbon sequestration programs.

5.1.3 Long-Term Policy Recommendations

With Pakistan's usually polarized political system, it is essential to depoliticize forest carbon sequestration by integrating it within bipartisan national agendas. Party affiliation, as revealed in the research, has little impact on economic effects perceptions this is a strategic window of opportunity for convergence of agendas. The long-term approach is to set up a National Forest Carbon Council under the Council of Common Interests (CCI) to ensure all provinces are included and that forestry-based climate policy is insulated against sudden political change. Environmental education must be incorporated into the national curriculum to create a common environmental ethic between generations and regions. National laws, like the Pakistan Climate Change Act, need to be extended to legally obligate all governments irrespective of political power to quantifiable forest carbon targets. This would, in the long run, stabilize forest-related economic policies and ensure continuity in climate action, regardless of political changes.

Highlights

- Public perception plays a crucial role in the economic impacts of FCS projects.
 - Government policy has a positive impact on forest carbon sequestration.
 - Ecosystem services enhance the economic justification of FCS.
 - Perceived project effectiveness mediates FCS impact pathways.
- Political affiliation shows no moderating effect on FCS outcomes.

References

- Ahmad, M. M., Imtiaz, M. A., Rasheed, F., Jameel, M. A., Asif, M., & Ahmad, H. (2023). The crucial role of forests in combating climate change. *Trends in Biotechnology and Plant Sciences*, 1(1), 1-6.
- Ali, S., Khan, S. M., Ahmad, Z., Siddiq, Z., Ullah, A., Yoo, S., Han, H., & Raposo, A. (2023). Carbon sequestration potential of different forest types in Pakistan and its role in regulating services for public health. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 1064586.
- Andrews, J., & Mulder, M. B. (2024). The Value of Failure: The Effect of an Expired REDD+ Conservation Program on Residents' Willingness for Future Participation. *Ecological Economics*, 220, 1-12.
- Annaufal, A. I., Mariyana, A. L. D., & Priyono, A. (2023). Market-Based Instruments for Environmental Management: A Comparative Analysis. *RSF Conference Series: Business, Management and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 19-23.
- Atmadja, S., Brockhaus, M., Seymour, F., & Pham, T. T. (2021). How do REDD+ projects contribute to the goals of the Paris Agreement? *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(12), 124066.
- Başkent, E. Z. (2023). Characterizing and assessing key ecosystem services in a representative forest ecosystem in Turkey. *Ecological Informatics*, 74, 101993.
- Bilal, M., Ali, W., Jamil, M., & Bashir, M. K. (2022). Impact of critical barriers on the stakeholder's adoption behavior toward green building technologies in Pakistan. *International Journal of Management Research and Emerging Sciences*, 13(1), 105-122.
- Block, A., Wezel, A., Schiechl, H., & Siebert, R. (2024). How to reduce the carbon footprint of the agricultural sector? Factors influencing farmers' decision to participate in carbon sequestration programs. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 359, 121019.

- Brander, L., van Beukering, P., & Eppink, F. (2024). Economic values for ecosystem services: A global synthesis and way forward. *Ecosystem Services*, 66, 101606.
- Cho, S., Baral, S., & Burlakoti, D. (2025). Afforestation/Reforestation and Avoided Conversion Carbon Projects in the United States. *Forests*, 16(1), 115.
- Daigneault, A., Simons-Legaard, E., & Weiskittel, A. (2024). Trade-offs and synergies of optimized management for maximizing carbon sequestration across complex landscapes and diverse ecosystem services. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 161, 103178.
- Don, A., Poeplau, C., Smith, P., & Conant, R. T. (2023). Carbon sequestration in soils and climate change mitigation—Definitions and pitfalls. *Global Change Biology*, 29(10), 2545–2558.
- Duncanson, L., Liang, M., Leitold, V., Armston, J., Krishna Moorthy, S. M., Dubayah, R., ... & Zvoleff, A. (2023). The effectiveness of global protected areas for climate change mitigation. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 2908.
- Enriquez-de-Salamanca, Á. (2024). Environmental and social impacts of carbon sequestration. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, 20(6), 1812–1838.
- Feitosa, T., Fernandes, M., Santos, C., da Silva, R., Garcia, J., Araújo Filho, R., Moura Aouada, M., & Rodrigues da Cunha, E. (2023). Assessing economic and ecological impacts of carbon stock and land use changes in Brazil's Amazon Forest: A 2050 projection. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 41, 703–713.
- Gao, L., Li, H., & Li, S. (2025). Effects on Carbon Sequestration of Biomass and Investment in State-Owned Forest Farms: A Case Study of Shaanxi Province, China. *Forests*, 16(1), 60.
- Ge, J., Zhang, Z. (J.), & Lin, B. (2023). Towards carbon neutrality: How much do forest carbon sinks cost in China? *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 98, 106949.
- Gelaye, Y. (2024). A systematic review on potential analogy of phytobiomass and soil carbon evaluation methods: Ethiopia insights. *Open Agriculture*, 9(1), 1–15.
- Goheer, M. A., Munir, M. A., Iqbal, M. M., & Rizwan, M. (2023). Assessment of change in forest land, carbon stock, and carbon emissions of KPK, Pakistan for past three decades using geospatial techniques. *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, 14(2), 442–453.
- Hao, F., Wang, Y., & Zhang, B. (2023). A study of American response to climate change and the influence of carbon dependency, social capital, and political orientation. *Society & Natural Resources*, 36(9), 1119–1139.
- Haya, B., Cullenward, D., Gillenwater, M., & Broekhoff, D. (2023). Comprehensive review of carbon quantification by improved forest management offset protocols. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, 6, 958879.
- Issa, A. (2023). Do emissions reduction initiatives improve financial performance? Empirical analysis of moderating factors. *International Journal of Accounting and Information Management*, 32, 228–257.
- Kamal, Asif & Yingjie, Ma & Ali, Ahmad. (2019). Significance of Billion Tree Tsunami Afforestation Project and Legal Developments in Forest Sector of Pakistan. 1. 157–165.
- Kasim, S., & Ghassan, M. (2023). Carbon Sequestration Through Forestry: A Differential Equation Approach. *Babylonian Journal of Mathematics*, 88–92.
- Ke, S., Zhang, Z., & Wang, Y. (2023). China's forest carbon sinks and mitigation potential from carbon sequestration trading perspective. *Ecological Indicators*, 148, 110054.
- Khan, A., Khan, N., Wahab, M., & Ahmed, M. (2019). Assessment of Sentinel-2-derived vegetation indices for the estimation of above-ground biomass/carbon stock, temporal deforestation, and carbon emissions estimation in the moist temperate forests of Pakistan. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*, 18(1), 783–815.
- Khan, I. A., Khan, W. R., Anwar, A., & Nazre, M. (2021). Assessment of above-ground biomass in Pakistan forest ecosystem's carbon pool: A review. *Forests*, 12(5), 586.

- Khan, M. A., Ali, S., Anser, M. K., Nassani, A. A., Al-Aiban, K. M., Rahman, S. U., & Zaman, (2024). From desolation to preservation: Investigating longitudinal trends in forest coverage and implications for future environmental strategies. *Helion*, 5, 1-18.
- Kocaglu, M., Ulucak, R., & Khan, S. A. R. (2024). Can forests realize the carbon neutrality dream? Evidence from a global sample. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 366, 121827.
- Li, C., Wu, J., Zhang, F., & Huang, X. (2025). Forest Carbon Sinks in Chinese Provinces and Their Impact on Sustainable Development Goals. *Forests*, 16(1), 83.
- Li, X., Zhang, H., Wang, J., & Chen, Y. (2022). Forest management plans for carbon sequestration. *Advances in Economics and Management Research*, 1(3), 227-232.
- Liu, Y., Chen, J., Zhang, L., & Xu, X. (2023). Future carbon sequestration and timber yields from Chinese commercial forests under shared socioeconomic pathways. *Forests*, 14(1), 1-20.
- Long, X., & Goulder, L. H. (2023). Carbon emission trading systems: a review of systems across the globe and a close look at China's national approach. *China Economic Journal*, 203-216.
- Lu, S., Lu, H., Zhang, C., Miao, C., & Kizos, T. (2025). Quantitative Impacts of Socio-Economic Changes on REDD+ Benefits in Xishuangbanna Rainforests. *Forests*, 16(1), 120.
- Lungarska, A., & Chakir, R. (2024). Projections of climate change impacts on ecosystem services and the role of land use adaptation in France. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators*, 22, 1-15.
- Ma, Y., Zhang, J., Li, H., & Wang, Y. (2023). The effect of the policy mix of green credit and government subsidy on environmental innovation. *Energy Economics*, 118, 106512.
- Masud, S., & Khan, A. (2024). Policy implementation barriers in climate change adaptation: The case of Pakistan. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 34(1), 42-52.
- Mei, B. (2023). Carbon offset as another driver of timberland investment returns in the United States. *Journal of Forest Business Research*, 2(1), 1-19.
- Meng, Y., Liu, Y., Zhang, Y., & Xu, H. (2023). China's climate change policy attention and forestry carbon sequestration growth. *Forests*, 14(11), 2273.
- Mirici, M. E., & Berberoglu, S. (2024). Terrestrial carbon dynamics and economic valuation of ecosystem service for land use management in the Mediterranean region. *Ecological Informatics*, 81, 102570.
- Moomaw, W. R., Masino, S. A., & Faison, E. K. (2020). Focus on the role of forests and soils in meeting climate change. *Environmental Research Letters*, 15(4), 040201.
- Morkovina, S., Sheshnitsan, S., Panyavina, E., Ivanova, A., & Kuznetsov, D. (2023). Opportunities and prospects for the implementation of reforestation climate projects in the forest steppe: An economic assessment. *Forests*, 14(8), 1611.
- Naik, A. & Roy, K. S. (2022). Mitigation of Climate Change Through Carbon Sequestration. In I. Management Association (Ed.), *Research Anthology on Environmental and Societal Impacts of Climate Change* (pp. 893-913). IGI Global Scientific Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-3686-8.ch044>
- Nantongo, M., Vatn, A., & Namirembe, S. (2024). REDD+: The perfect marriage between conservation and development? A comparative study of the impacts of REDD+ on livelihoods and deforestation in Tanzania. *World Development*, 173, 106432.
- Nolander, C., & Lundmark, R. (2024). A Review of Forest Ecosystem Services and Their Spatial Value Characteristics. *Forests*, 15(6), 919.
- Olha, V., Volodymyr, T., & Svitlana, M. (2024). Innovative models of green entrepreneurship: Social impact on sustainable development of local economies. *Economics Ecology Socium*, 8(1), 89-111.

- Pakina, O. (2024). Forest carbon projects: Economic and environmental dimensions. In *The 5th Congress of Slavic Geographers and Ethnographers* (p. 47). <https://doi.org/10.46793/csge5.28ap>
- Pan, Y., Zhang, Y., Chen, J., & Wang, W. (2023). Canada's green gold: Unveiling challenges, opportunities, and pathways for sustainable forestry offsets. *Forests*, 14(11), 2206.
- Pragati, V., & Ghosh, P. K. (2022). The economics of forest carbon sequestration: A bibliometric analysis. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1236338/v2>
- Prati, R., & Pomeroy, A. (2022). Forest restoration and reforestation initiatives. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Education Research*, 4(1):07-10
- Qian, M., Zhang, J., & Li, H. (2023). Computer decision model for maximum carbon sequestration using analytic hierarchy process and fuzzy comprehensive appraisal. *Academic Journal of Computing & Information Science*, 6(4), 77-83.
- Raihan, A. (2023). Sustainable Development in Europe: A Review of the Forestry Sector's Social, Environmental, and Economic Dynamics. *Global Sustainability Research*, 2(3), 72-92.
- Rajasugunasekar, P., Kumar, S., & Ramasamy, R. (2023). An integrative review for the role of forests in combating climate change and promoting sustainable development. *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*, 13(11), 4331-4341.
- Roy, A., & Bhan, M. (2024). Forest carbon market-based mechanisms in India: Learnings from global design principles and domestic barriers to implementation. *Ecological Indicators*, 158, 1-11.
- Russo, M., Tonti, M., Giaccio, V., & Testi, A. (2023). Forest ecosystem services: Economic evaluation of carbon sequestration on a large scale. *Valori e Valutazioni*, 33, 17-30.
- Sawaid, M., Shah, M. A., Ullah, S., Abbas, S., & Riaz, A. (2023). Monitoring of large-scale forest restoration: Evidence of vegetation recovery and reversing chronic ecosystem degradation in the mountain region of Pakistan. *Ecological Informatics*, 77, 102277.
- Setiawan, A. A., Nugroho, P. D., & Saptomo, S. K. (2024). Unraveling land use land cover change, their driving factors, and implication on carbon storage through an integrated modelling approach. *The Egyptian Journal of Remote Sensing and Space Sciences*, 27(4), 616-627.
- Shen, L., Song, X., Wang, Y., & Ma, C. (2023). Unravelling the role of institutions in market-based instruments: A systematic review on forest carbon mechanisms. *Forests*, 14(1), 136.
- Shrivastava, A., Shrivastava, S., & Dwivedi, A. (2024). Clean Development Mechanism: Indian step sustainable environment. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 491, 02017.
- Soares-Filho, B. S., Oliveira, U., Ferreira, M. N., Marques, F. F. C., de Oliveira, A. R., Silva, F. R., & Börner, J. (2023). Contribution of the Amazon Protected Areas Program to forest conservation. *Biological Conservation*, 279, 109928.
- Söderholm, P. (2020). The green economy transition: The challenges of technological change for sustainability. *Sustainable Earth*, 3(1), 6.
- Štraus, D., Diaci, J., & Roženbergar, D. (2023). Identifying optimal forest management maximizing carbon sequestration in mountain forests impacted by natural disturbances: A case study in the Alps. *Forests*, 14(5), 947.
- Suhardono, D., Wicaksono, A., & Widayati, A. (2024). Carbon sequestration and environmental service assessment in the special purpose forest area of Mount Bromo, Indonesia. *Journal of Ecological Engineering*, 25(4), 14-22.
- Sun, J., Li, G., Zhang, Y., Qin, W., & Chai, G. (2023). Assessment of suitable areas for afforestation and its carbon sink value in fragile ecological areas of northern China. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 348, 119401.

- Szajko, D., Raczowska, J., & Stryamets, N. (2024). The role of price incentives in enhancing carbon sequestration in the forestry sector of Hungary. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 158, 103097.
- Verma, M., Kandwal, R., & Pandey, S. K. (2024). Forest carbon sequestration mapping and economic quantification infusing MLPnn-Markov chain and InVEST carbon model in Askot Wildlife Sanctuary, Western Himalaya. *Ecological Informatics*, 79, 102428.
- Waleed, R., Qamer, F. M., Abbas, S., & Shehzad, K. (2024). Urbanization-led land cover change impacts terrestrial carbon storage capacity: A high-resolution remote sensing-based nationwide assessment in Pakistan (1990–2020). *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 105, 107396.
- West, T. A. P., Christopher, B. C., & Ellis, P. W. (2023). Action needed to make carbon offsets from forest conservation work for climate change mitigation. *Science*, 381(6660), 873–877.
- Wester, J., & Macdonald, C. (2023). Perceptions of environmental problems and solutions in Florida across sectors: A survey of key stakeholders and the public. *Ambio*, 52, 1098-1111.
- Yadav, K., & Yadav, A. V. (2023). Creating economic incentives for agroforestry in Assam. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 149, 102928.
- Yin, R. (2024). *Global Forest Carbon: Policy, Economics and Finance* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003436652>
- You, M., Huang, Y., Wu, N., & Yuan, X. (2025). Efficiency Evaluation and Resource Optimization of Forestry Carbon Sequestration Projects: A Case Study of State-Owned Forest Farms in Fujian Province. *Sustainability*, 17(1), 375.
- Zafar, Z., Khan, S. M., Khan, A. A., & Ullah, S. (2023). Predictive modeling of regional carbon storage dynamics in response to land use/land cover changes: An InVEST-based analysis. *Ecological Informatics*, 80, 102701.
- Zhang, Y., Liu, Y., Li, X., & Wang, Y. (2023). Impact of carbon sequestration by terrestrial vegetation on economic growth: Evidence from Chinese county satellite data. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1369.
- Zhang, Y., Zhao, W., Wang, Z., & Liu, J. (2023). Optimizing carbon sequestration in forest management plans using advanced algorithms: A case study of Greater Khingan Mountains. *Forests*, 14(9), 1785.
- Zhao, Y., Li, K., & Tang, Y. (2023). How does environmentally induced R&D affect carbon productivity? A government support perspective. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 88, 924–961.
- Zhou, J., Liu, J., Gao, J., & Xu, Q. (2024). Carbon sequestration costs and spatial spillover effects in China's collective forests. *Carbon Balance and Management*, 19(14), 1–16.
- Zhu, D., Peters, G. P., Friedlingstein, P., & Le Quéré, C. (2024). Global carbon emissions in 2023. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 5, 253–254.
- Zijie Ji, (2023). Research on the value and economic value of forest ecological carbon sequestration. *Highlights in Business, Economics and Management*, 5, 592-599.